

CTD Processing Report for the July 2018 ASCA/ SEAmester survey

Laura Braby (lv.braby@saeon.nrf.ac.za)

1. Introduction

This report contains a detailed description of the correction applied to the quality-controlled, processed CTD salinity data from the July 2018 ASCA/ SEAmester survey. After the cruise, we were unable to find a salinometer and suitable temperature controlled laboratory in which to run the salinity samples collected from the Niskin bottles and unfortunately this delayed the running of the samples by almost 1 year. A previous study by Kawano (2010) found that the double conductivity ratio of their salinity samples increased linearly with storage time. They estimated that the error caused by evaporation was equivalent to 0.0014 PSU over a period of 87 days. It is therefore necessary for us to consider the impact of a ~ 1 year storage time on our results.

Figure 1: The effect of storage time on the double conductivity ratio of salinity samples. 40 samples were drawn from 1 Niskin bottle, and 10 samples were run after 1, 33, 66 and 87 days of storage. Error bars show the standard deviation (Source: Kawano, 2010).

Once the UCT Portasal had been calibrated overseas and transported safely back to Cape Town, the samples were run in May and June 2019 by Kay McMonigal, Laura Braby, Jordan van Stavel and Tahlia Henry. On the second day of running the samples, a cable tie came loose inside the salinometer, resulting in the bath water mixing with the salinity samples. This meant that the Portasal had to be drained, moved, fixed and recalibrated before we could resume running the samples.

In addition to the correction of the quality-controlled, processed salinity data according to the method described by Shane Elipot in the “Extended report on CTD processing for ASCA0618” (also used for analysing the July 2016 ASCA/ SEAmester CTD salinity data), it is necessary for us to consider if the delay in running the samples has an effect on the quality of the data, as well as if the recalibration of the Portasal mid way through running the samples has a significant impact on our results.

2. Data

The raw data were processed by James Maitland according to best practice methods, using the Sea-Bird software. To correct the quality-controlled, processed CTD salinity data, we use 164 collected salinity samples, where the 3 consecutive double conductivity ratio (X2R) readings taken for each sample did not differ by more than 0.002. Conductivity was calculated using the TEOS-10 MATLAB toolbox. For each sample, the median value of the three conductivity values was taken as the final sample value.

To begin, we analyse the Standard Seawater Sample readings that were recorded before, during and after the salinity samples were run to determine whether or not there was a drift in the Portasal. From Figure 2 we observe that the drift before the salinometer broke (days 1 and 2) appears to be very different from after it was fixed (days 21-23).

We therefore separate the data into the first (Batch 1 of samples run) and second (Batch 2 of samples run) calibrations of the salinometer as shown by Figure 3 and correct the drift separately for each batch of samples.

Figure 2: The double conductivity ratio for standard seawater samples showing original values, the drift estimate, the corrected values and the reference $2 \times K_{15}$ value.

Figure 3: Double conductivity ratio for standard seawater samples showing original values, the drift estimate, the corrected values, and the reference $2 \times K_{15}$ value for a) Batch 1 and b) Batch 2, c) and d) indicate salinity of the SW for Batch 1 and 2 respectively

We compare the salinity samples with the Niskin bottle files from 2 different sets of CTD sensors (hereafter referred to as CTD1 and CTD2). From Figure 4 it is apparent that all 3 datasets are overall in good agreement with each other. We remove the 3 large obvious outliers from the dataset as they affect the end result of the regression.

Figure 4: Salinity differences between the Portasal and CTD. Portasal – Portasal values are indicated in black, Portasal- CTD1 in blue and Portasal CTD2 are indicated in red (3 large outliers have been removed).

3. Comparisons of Portasal and CTD conductivity values

For 15 of the 161 calculated values, the difference of conductivity is greater than 0.003 mS/cm, the expected initial accuracy of the CTD sensors. These sample values are discarded from the regression analyses used to correct the CTD conductivity.

We plot the difference in CTD and Portasal conductivity as functions of conductivity, pressure, time (or Cast Number) and temperature (Figure 5) and perform a linear regression for each case. Results indicate that differences of conductivity between the CTD and the samples are significant functions of conductivity, time and temperature but not of pressure. Table 1 below shows the slope of the data.

Table 1: The slope and y-intercept of the data represented in Figure 5 ($y = mx + c$)

Conductivity differences as a function of:	CTD 1 slope; intercept	CTD2 slope; intercept
Conductivity	-1.3322e-04; 0.0061	-1.9764e-04; 0.0093
Pressure	3.9278e-07; 0.0011	-9.7792e-08; 0.0014
Cast Number	-3.4468e-04; 0.0046	-3.2237e-04; 0.0050
Temperature	-9.0816e-05; 0.0017	-1.5185e-04; 0.0031

Figure 5: Conductivity differences between CTD and Portasal values and as a function of a) Conductivity, b) Pressure, c) Cast Number and d) Temperature.

4. Regression

As per the July 2016 ASCA/SEAmester CTD processing report, we derive coefficients for the following correction models for CTD1 and CTD2:

Model A: $C_C = \alpha C + \gamma$

Model AA: $C_C = \alpha C$

Model B: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P + \gamma$

Model BB: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta P$

Model C: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T + \gamma$

Model CC: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta T$

Model D: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta t + \gamma$

Model DD: $C_C = \alpha C + \beta t$

Where C represents conductivity, P represents pressure, T represents temperature and t represents time. α , β and γ are derived for both CTD1 and CTD2 using the least squares method, regressing the CTD data against the sample calculated conductivity. For models AA, BB, CC and DD γ is equal to 0.

For all models, and for both sets of sensors the adjusted R^2 value was almost equal to 1. Model C reveals adjusted R^2 values that are slightly closer to 1 than the other models, for both sets of CTD sensors (Table 2, which shows 1- the adjusted R^2 value). We therefore opt to correct the data according to model C.

Table 2: Adjusted R squared values from the different models for CTD1 and CTD2

CTD1		CTD2	
Model	[1- Adjusted R²]	Model	[1- Adjusted R²]
A1	0.7611e-05	A2	0.7634e-05
AA1	0.7578e-05	AA2	0.7629e-05
B1	0.7548e-05	B2	0.7577e-05
BB1	0.7628e-05	BB2	0.7681e-05
C1	0.7508e-05	C2	0.7536e-05
CC1	0.7621e-05	CC2	0.7650e-05
D1	0.7550e-05	D2	0.7578e-05
DD1	0.7576e-05	DD2	0.7648e-05

Figures 6 and 7 below show a graphical representation of the results for the correction model C.

Figure 6: Results of regression for conductivity for model C after removing large residuals.

Figure 7: Results of regression for salinity for model C after removing large residuals.

Table 3: Results from second regression for conductivity and salinity for model C.

	Sensor Set 1	Sensor Set 2
α	1.0012	1.0012
β	-0.0012	-0.0012
$\hat{\sigma}$ Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.0040	0.0043
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU)	0.0037	0.0040
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU) for P>2000 dbar	0.0018	0.0018
$\hat{\sigma}$ Salinity (PSU) for P<2000 dbar	0.0042	0.0044

$\hat{\sigma}$ is the square root of the mean square error (an estimate of the final error or uncertainty for conductivity). The error for conductivity is more than 3×10^{-3} mS/cm for both sensors. We further estimate $\hat{\sigma}$ for salinity and find that for model C the error is almost 2 times the required accuracy of 0.002 for international standards. However, when we separate the error by salinities with pressure less than 2000 dbar and pressure greater than 2000 dbar, we find that we have achieved the required accuracy for P > 2000 dbar.

We find CTD sensor set 1 to be slightly more accurate and therefore chose to correct the data according to CTD1.

5. Finalising the data

Once the drift from the salinometer had been corrected, the July 2018 ASCA/ SEAmester data from the CTD and the salinity samples are found to be in good agreement with each other. For the final dataset we correct the CTD data according to model C.

Despite the ~1 year delay in running the samples the data from this survey compare well with the data from the ACT surveys which took place between 2010- 2013 (Figure 8). Particularly for the deeper water masses, where the salinity values do not vary much we found that the values of the salinity samples fell within the expected range. We corrected

the data from CTD sensor set 1 according to model C for the final data set for the July 2018 ASCA/ SEAmester survey.

Figure 8: T-S diagram comparing the ACT data to the July 2018 ASCA/ SEAmester data. Dark blue, orange and yellow dots correspond to the ACT data. Purple dots indicate the uncorrected data, where as green dots show the data corrected according to model C. Light blue dots are a T-S of the salinity sample data. The right hand panel is a close up of the left.